

Wall material for an energy-efficient ecological one-story house

Today, the issue of environmental friendliness is gaining popularity, more people resort to conscious consumption of natural resources.

The issue of ecological housing has several components - it is safety for human health, creation of optimal comfortable conditions, ecology of natural resources and environmental safety.

When constructing an ecological building, you need to be clearly aware of how ecological it will actually be, how many resources will be spent on delivering building materials, how well the materials pass air and whether they are heat-conductive, contain harmful substances, and how they are disposed of.

The paper considers the justification of the wall material for an energy-efficient ecological one-story house. The use of modern ecological materials is proposed on the example of a 3D house model project created in the Autodesk Fusion 360 software product (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 – 3D model of an energy-efficient ecological house

The design object is to create a house from environmentally friendly materials that are safe for human health and do not pose a threat to the environment.

The main advantages of cinderblock houses:

1. Resistance to changes in temperature and humidity level.
2. Environmental friendliness.

3. Keeps heat well inside.
4. High level of sound insulation.
5. Increased thermal conductivity.
6. Term of operation.

Today, building a house from cinder blocks is characterized by exceptional quality and durability, compared to other materials.

Thanks to modern technologies, houses made of bricks or soil blocks are built not only qualitatively, but also quite quickly. Walls made of cinder blocks are resistant to fire, have high heat-insulating properties, protect against insect damage, and have a service life of about 100 years.

To increase durability and service life, it is necessary to choose the most appropriate type of concrete. Depending on the choice of this material, it is necessary to push back in terms of warming the walls and increasing the thermal insulation properties.

Selection of bricks, namely soil blocks for wall material. The composition of soil blocks is peat, sand, ash, needles and sawdust. In addition to the completely natural composition, they perfectly absorb excess moisture in the house and release the accumulated moisture when the temperature changes, if necessary.

Regarding the comparison of the composition of cinderblocks with bricks, cinderblocks have a higher soil content and use cement as a binder. Bricks are made from clay and sand without adding cement.

Soil blocks and bricks are two different building materials with their own unique characteristics and composition.

Soil blocks are made from a mixture of soil, cement, sand and other additives. The main component is soil, which can be collected at the construction site or purchased. Cement is used as a binding material to bind the soil together. Additives can include various substances to improve the properties of the blocks, such as plasticizers, moisture retainers or refractory additives.

Bricks, on the other hand, are made from clay or other ceramic materials. The composition of clay bricks includes clay, sand and water. After the brick is formed,

it goes through the process of drying and firing in special ovens. This process gives the brick strength and durability, but is significantly inferior to its fire-resistant properties.

Comparative characteristics of soil blocks and bricks are presented in table_1.

Table 1 – Comparison of the composition of soil blocks and bricks

Склад	Грунтоблоки	Цегла
1	Ґрунт	Ґлина
2	Зола	Пісок
3	Пісок	Цемент
4	Тирса	Пластифікатор

Eco-concrete differs from traditional concrete in some features that ensure its environmental friendliness and sustainability. Eco-concrete is a building material that consists of cement, lime or gypsum, as well as additional components that ensure its environmental friendliness and improve its properties. Eco-concrete may contain secondary materials such as fly ash, slag, ground glass fiber or other waste products resulting from other manufacturing processes. The use of these materials helps to reduce the consumption of natural resources and waste, and also reduces emissions into the atmosphere.

The main components of eco-concrete may include the following:

1. Cement is the main component of eco-concrete. Portland cement is usually used, which is the main binder for binding other components together. Cement is responsible for the hardening and strength of concrete.

2. Lime or gypsum - lime and gypsum are biodegradable and environmentally safe materials.

3. Regenerative or secondary materials - may contain secondary materials such as fly ash, slag, ground glass fiber or other waste materials that can be used as a partial or complete replacement for cement. The use of such materials helps to reduce the consumption of natural resources and waste.

4. Aggregates – sand, crushed stone or crushed stone are added to provide the mass and structure of the concrete. Aggregates must have appropriate fractions and quality to achieve the required properties of concrete.

5. Water - used to activate cement and create a chemical reaction that leads to concrete hardening. It is important to maintain the correct ratio of water and cement to achieve optimal properties of concrete.

Concrete and cement are components of eco-concrete, but their composition and properties may differ.

Traditional concrete consists of cement, sand aggregate (sand) and stone or crushed stone aggregates. Cement is used as a binding agent added to the mixture to bind the aggregates together and form a solid mass. The typical composition of traditional concrete is about 10-15% cement, 60-75% sand and 15-30% stone or crushed stone aggregates.

A comparison of the composition of eco-concrete and concrete is shown in Table 2.

Table 2 - Comparison of the composition of eco-concrete and concrete

Склад	Екобетон	Бетон
1	Цемент	Цемент
2	Пісок	Пісок
3	Вода	Гравій
4	Шлак	Пластифікатор
5	Натуральне волокно	Камінь

Eco-concrete, on the other hand, is used to refer to concrete that uses special admixtures or additives to lower the cement content and improve its environmental performance. The addition of environmental additives can reduce the amount of cement in concrete, improve its energy efficiency and corrosion resistance. Such additives can be plant-based, such as rice ash, or secondary materials that result from waste processing, such as reclaimed fly ash.

The main advantages of eco-concrete compared to traditional concrete are reduced use of natural resources, reduced CO2 emissions during production and operation, improved energy efficiency and the production of less waste. Thus, eco-concrete contributes to sustainable construction and reducing the negative impact of the construction industry on the environment.

Eco-concrete and ordinary concrete are two different materials with different composition and properties. Here is a comparison of the composition of eco-concrete and concrete:

Composition of eco-concrete:

1. Cement is the main binding component in eco-concrete. It is responsible for the hardening and strengthening of concrete.
2. Sand - used as a filler in eco-concrete. It provides structural strength and stability of concrete.
3. Water - water is necessary for the reaction of cement and hardening of concrete. It also helps in the process of mixing and distributing the components.

The composition of ordinary concrete:

1. Cement is the main binding component in ordinary concrete.
2. Sand - used as a filler in ordinary concrete.
3. Stone or crushed stone - added to concrete to improve its strength and structural stability.

However, it is important to note that the composition of concrete can vary depending on the specific type of concrete and the manufacturer's specifications. Different types of concrete have different properties, such as strength, ductility, weather resistance, and others

After analyzing the composition of soil blocks and eco-concrete and making a comparison, they justified the choice of these materials for the wall material of an energy-efficient ecological one-story house, due to good energy-efficient and fire-resistant properties due to the natural composition, which do not harm the environment.